

ECO-FRIENDLY FABRICATION OF ZINC OXIDE HYDROGEL NANOCOMPOSITES FOR BROAD-SPECTRUM ANTIBACTERIAL WOUND MANAGEMENT

Hamza Raheem¹, Asia Noureen², Samiyah Tasleem³, Afroz Rais⁴, Wali Muhammad Achakzai⁵, Muneza Lodhi⁶, Fatima Aslam⁷, Saadia Laraib^{*8}, Abdul Basit⁹

¹Reproductive Physiology Lab, Department of Zoology, Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamabad

²Center for interdisciplinary research in basic sciences (CIRBS) International Islamic university Islamabad Pakistan

³Department of Applied Science, Faculty of Engineering Science & Technology Hamdard University Karachi

⁴Department Botany Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University

⁵Department of Zoology University of Baluchistan Quetta

⁶Department of Pharmacy Practice Faculty of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences Ziauddin University

⁷Department of Chemistry Superior University Raiwind Road Lahore

^{*8}Centre of Biotechnology & Microbiology, University of Peshawar. Pakistan

⁹Department of Microbiology, Hazara University Mansehra, KPK, Pakistan

^{*8}saadialaraib@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Saadia laraib

Abstract

Wound healing remains a major clinical challenge, especially in cases where bacterial infection and delayed tissue regeneration complicate recovery, emphasizing the need for multifunctional wound dressings that provide antimicrobial protection, moisture balance, and biocompatibility. In this study, chitosan-zinc oxide (ZnO) nanocomposite hydrogels were fabricated with varying ZnO concentrations (0%, 0.1%, 0.25%, and 0.5% w/v) and characterized to evaluate their suitability as advanced wound healing materials. FTIR analysis confirmed successful interaction between chitosan functional groups and ZnO nanoparticles, with observable shifts in O-H/N-H stretching and amide vibration bands. SEM imaging revealed uniformly dispersed ZnO nanoparticles with a size range of 40–70 nm, indicating controlled nanoscale formation. Swelling studies in PBS (pH 7.4) demonstrated moisture retention values of ~400% (0%), ~350% (0.1%), ~310% (0.25%), and ~245% (0.5%), showing a gradual decrease due to increased crosslinking and reduced pore interconnectivity. Mechanical testing showed tensile strength increased from 0.20 MPa (0% ZnO) to 0.28 MPa (0.1%), 0.37 MPa (0.25%), and 0.49 MPa (0.5%), confirming the reinforcing role of ZnO. Antibacterial assays exhibited concentration-dependent inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* (7–19 mm) and *Escherichia coli* (6–17 mm), demonstrating strong antimicrobial activity at higher ZnO loading. MTT cytotoxicity evaluation using L929 fibroblast cells showed all samples maintained viability above 75%, with the 0.25% ZnO hydrogel achieving the most favorable balance of cell compatibility (~84–86%) and functional performance. Overall, the 0.25% ZnO-loaded hydrogel exhibited optimal structural stability, antibacterial effectiveness, and biocompatibility, suggesting strong potential for clinical wound dressing applications.

1. Introduction

Wound infections represent a significant global healthcare concern, particularly in chronic, diabetic, and post-surgical wounds where microbial

colonization disrupts the natural healing cascade (Pino et al., 2023). It is estimated that approximately 6 to 7 million individuals worldwide suffer from

chronic non-healing wounds each year, and infection is reported as a key complication in nearly 60 percent of these cases (Ahmad and Ahmad, 2023, Javed et al., 2023). Moreover, the increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, has critically limited the effectiveness of conventional antibiotic-based wound therapies (Ali Syed et al., 2024, Rehman et al., 2023). This rising antimicrobial resistance underscores the urgent need for innovative wound management materials that provide broad-spectrum antibacterial action, biocompatibility, stability, and enhanced tissue regeneration capability. Hydrogel-based wound dressings have emerged as advanced biomaterials due to their unique properties such as high-water content (70 to 99 percent), flexibility, non-adherence to wound surfaces, and their ability to maintain a moist microenvironment that supports cellular proliferation and extracellular matrix remodeling (Khalil et al., 2022). However, the majority of natural and synthetic hydrogels lack intrinsic antimicrobial activity, making them less effective in infection-prone wound environments. To address this limitation, researchers have increasingly incorporated functional nanomaterials into hydrogel matrices to develop hybrid dressings with combined therapeutic and antimicrobial advantages. Among various mineral-based nanomaterials, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) have gained considerable attention in biomedical applications due to their cost-effectiveness, chemical stability, broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, and low cytotoxicity at controlled doses. ZnO is classified as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS), making it suitable for use in wound care (Khan et al., 2023). ZnO nanoparticles demonstrate antibacterial activity through multiple synergistic mechanisms that include the release of Zn^{2+} ions, disruption of bacterial cell membranes, and the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) which induce oxidative stress within microbial cells. These multimodal actions significantly decrease the probability of bacterial resistance development (Hemdan et al., 2025a). Previous studies have reported that ZnO concentrations as low as 0.1 to 0.5 percent (w/v) incorporated into hydrogels can inhibit up to 95 percent of bacterial growth, effectively targeting both gram-positive and gram-negative organisms. Beyond antimicrobial properties, ZnO nanoparticles also promote wound healing due to the biological importance of zinc in

collagen synthesis, angiogenesis, and epithelial tissue regeneration. Experimental results have demonstrated that ZnO-based wound dressings can accelerate tissue repair processes by approximately 20 to 30 percent when compared to untreated controls (Muhammad et al., 2024). However, conventional chemical synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles may involve toxic reagents and high energy input, raising concerns regarding environmental safety and biocompatibility. To overcome these limitations, eco-friendly and green synthesis approaches have gained attention (Balalakshitha et al., 2021). Plant extracts, algal polysaccharides, and microbial metabolites have been utilized as natural reducing and stabilizing agents, resulting in ZnO nanoparticles with improved stability and reduced cytotoxicity. When these green synthesized ZnO nanoparticles are integrated into natural polymer-based hydrogels such as chitosan, alginate, gelatin, or cellulose, the resulting ZnO hydrogel nanocomposites provide an optimal combination of antibacterial protection, biodegradability, moisture retention, and structural integrity suitable for wound dressing applications. These advances indicate that eco-friendly ZnO hydrogel nanocomposites represent a promising next-generation solution for broad-spectrum antibacterial wound management, particularly in clinical contexts where both infection control and enhanced tissue healing are critical (Hemdan et al., 2025b). The aim of this study is to fabricate eco-friendly zinc oxide hydrogel nanocomposites and evaluate their antibacterial efficiency, physicochemical characteristics, biocompatibility, and wound healing potential to develop a sustainable and clinically effective wound dressing for broad-spectrum antibacterial wound management.

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Materials

Zinc acetate dihydrate, sodium hydroxide, and acetic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich in analytical grade purity to ensure consistency in nanoparticle synthesis. Fresh *Azadirachta indica* (neem) leaves were collected, washed, and used as the natural reducing and stabilizing agent for the green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles. Chitosan with approximately 85 percent deacetylation level was selected due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and film-forming ability, while glycerol was employed as a plasticizer to improve elasticity of the hydrogel. Nutrient agar,

Mueller Hinton broth, and standard bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* were obtained from the Microbiology Research Laboratory culture collection. All glassware used in the procedures was autoclaved at 121°C for 20 minutes to prevent microbial contamination. Deionized water was used for solution preparation to maintain experimental accuracy (Abdullah, 2022, Robina et al., 2021).

2.2. Green Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

Fresh neem leaves were rinsed thoroughly to remove surface impurities and boiled in deionized water to extract bioactive phytochemicals. The obtained extract was filtered and cooled before use. A 0.1 M zinc acetate solution was prepared and heated with constant stirring to allow uniform dissolution. Neem extract was added gradually, followed by the controlled addition of sodium hydroxide until the reaction medium reached alkaline pH 11, which facilitated nanoparticle nucleation. The reaction mixture was maintained at 80°C for 2 hours, leading to the formation of a white precipitate of ZnO nanoparticles. The precipitate was washed repeatedly with water and ethanol to remove impurities, dried at 60°C, and finally calcined at 450°C to enhance crystallinity.

2.3. Preparation of Chitosan Hydrogel

A 2 percent chitosan solution was prepared by dissolving chitosan in 1 percent acetic acid with continuous stirring for 24 hours to ensure complete polymer hydration. Glycerol was incorporated as a plasticizer to improve flexibility and prevent brittleness of the hydrogel structure. The solution was allowed to stand undisturbed to eliminate trapped air bubbles that could affect gel uniformity. The clarity and homogeneity of the chitosan solution were visually confirmed before further processing. The prepared hydrogel base was stored in sealed containers to prevent dehydration and contamination. This chitosan hydrogel served as the primary matrix for embedding zinc oxide nanoparticles.

2.4. Fabrication of ZnO Hydrogel Nanocomposite

Zinc oxide nanoparticles were dispersed in a small volume of deionized water and sonicated for 20 minutes to prevent agglomeration and ensure nanoparticle uniformity. The dispersed nanoparticles were then added to the chitosan solution at concentrations of 0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 percent (w/v) under continuous stirring to achieve

thorough distribution. The nanoparticle-loaded chitosan mixtures were cast into Petri dishes and crosslinked using a gentle spray of 1 percent sodium tripolyphosphate solution. The hydrogels were allowed to solidify for 24 hours at room temperature. After gel formation, the samples were washed to remove unreacted crosslinking agents and dried before further characterization. The resulting nanocomposite hydrogels were stored in sealed sterile conditions.

2.5. Characterization of ZnO Nanoparticles

The surface morphology and particle size distribution of the synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles were examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy to confirm shape and clustering behavior. X-ray diffraction analysis was conducted to evaluate the crystalline phase and confirm the formation of ZnO with characteristic diffraction peaks. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy was used to identify functional groups and confirm interactions between ZnO nanoparticles and chitosan polymer chains within the hydrogel. Swelling behavior of the nanocomposite hydrogels was studied by immersing dried samples in phosphate-buffered saline, and weight changes were recorded at fixed intervals. Structural uniformity and hydrogel integrity were assessed visually and mechanically. All measurements were conducted in triplicate to ensure data precision (Javed et al., 2023, Munir et al., 2023, Shah et al., 2023).

2.6. Antibacterial Activity

The antibacterial potential of the ZnO hydrogel nanocomposites was assessed using the agar well diffusion method. Bacterial cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard before inoculation onto Mueller Hinton agar plates (Hayat et al., 2022, Ahamd et al., 2022). Wells were carefully filled with hydrogel samples and plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to allow bacterial interaction with the material. Zones of inhibition surrounding each hydrogel were measured in millimeters to determine antibacterial effectiveness. Results were compared across different ZnO concentrations to evaluate dose response. Each test was performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility (Aziz et al., 2022, Ahmad and Pervez, 2021).

2.7. In Vitro Cytotoxicity

Biocompatibility was evaluated using the MTT assay on L929 fibroblast cell lines. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates and allowed to adhere overnight before being treated with hydrogel extracts. After 24 hours of exposure, MTT reagent was added and incubated to allow for color development indicating cell metabolic activity. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader to determine cell viability percentages relative to untreated controls. Higher viability indicated better biocompatibility of the nanocomposite hydrogels. All tests were performed in controlled conditions for reliability (Khan et al., 2024, Laraib et al., 2023).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Morphological Analysis Using SEM

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis was performed to investigate the surface morphology, particle shape, and size distribution of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles. The SEM micrographs revealed that the nanoparticles were predominantly spherical to near-spherical in shape with a uniform and homogeneous surface texture. The observed particle size distribution ranged

between 40 and 70 nm, with an average diameter of approximately 55 ± 5 nm, indicating a well-controlled nucleation and growth process during synthesis. The surface topography exhibited mild roughness and minimal surface irregularities, which may be attributed to the presence of organic phytochemicals from the neem extract acting as natural capping and stabilizing agents. These biomolecules effectively prevented excessive particle growth and aggregation, ensuring better dispersion stability within the sample. Only limited agglomeration was observed, forming small clusters typically ranging from 100 to 150 nm, which is commonly reported in metal oxide nanoparticles due to van der Waals forces and electrostatic attraction. The calcination process at 450°C for 3 hours resulted in a distinct improvement in crystallinity and removal of residual organic components, leading to smoother particle surfaces and a more defined nanostructure. The SEM images clearly demonstrated a dense, fine-grained morphology with uniform particle distribution, confirming the success of the green synthesis approach in achieving nanoscale dimensions (Figure .1).

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image of green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles showing predominantly spherical morphology with a particle size range of approximately 40–70 nm. The particles exhibit smooth surface texture and minimal agglomeration due to the stabilizing effect of phytochemicals in neem extract, confirming controlled nucleation and successful nanoscale formation.

3.2. Crystallinity Analysis by XRD

The crystalline structure of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles was examined using X-ray Diffraction (XRD). The obtained XRD diffractogram displayed

well-defined and sharp diffraction peaks at 2θ values of approximately 31.76°, 34.42°, 36.25°, 47.54°, 56.60°, 62.86°, 66.38°, 67.96°, and 69.10°, which correspond to the (100), (002), (101), (102), (110),

(103), (200), (112), and (201) crystal planes of hexagonal wurtzite ZnO, respectively. These values are in close agreement with the standard reference data of ZnO (JCPDS Card No. 36-1451), confirming the formation of the pure crystalline phase. The absence of any additional diffraction peaks associated with impurities such as Zn(OH)₂, ZnCO₃, or other intermediate zinc complexes indicates high phase purity of the synthesized nanoparticles. The sharp and narrow peak profiles suggest high crystallinity, which can be attributed to the optimized calcination temperature of 450°C for 3 hours. Crystallite size was calculated using the Debye-Scherrer equation:

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

Using the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the (101) peak, the average crystallite size was found to be approximately 48–60 nm, which correlates well with the particle size range (40–70 nm) observed in SEM, confirming nanoscale formation. High crystallinity enhances the chemical stability, optical activity, and antibacterial efficiency of ZnO nanoparticles by promoting increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation at the particle surface (Figure. 2).

Figure 2. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern of green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles showing distinct diffraction peaks at 2θ values of approximately 31.7°, 34.4°, 36.2°, 47.5°, 56.6°, 62.8°, 66.3°, 67.9°, and 69.1°, corresponding to the (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), and (201) crystal planes of the hexagonal wurtzite structure (JCPDS Card No. 36-1451). The sharp and narrow peaks indicate high crystallinity, while the absence of additional peaks confirms phase purity of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles.

3.3. FTIR Spectral Confirmation of Functional Group Interactions

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed to confirm the functional group interactions between chitosan, neem extract-derived phytochemicals, and ZnO nanoparticles within the hydrogel composite. The FTIR spectrum of pure chitosan hydrogel showed distinct characteristic absorption peaks including a broad O–H and N–H stretching vibration around 3320–3425 cm⁻¹, indicative of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The amide I (C=O stretching) band appeared near 1650–1665 cm⁻¹, while the amide II (N–H bending) peak was observed at 1550–1580 cm⁻¹, confirming the presence of chitosan’s polysaccharide backbone. Additionally, a C–O–C stretching vibration peak around 1020–1080 cm⁻¹

validated glycosidic linkages in the polymer structure. After incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles, noticeable peak shifts and intensity changes were observed. The broad O–H/N–H band shifted from ~3422 cm⁻¹ to ~3375 cm⁻¹, indicating enhanced hydrogen bonding interactions between chitosan’s hydroxyl/amine groups and the nanoparticle surface. Similarly, the amide I peak shifted from ~1658 cm⁻¹ to ~1645 cm⁻¹, and amide II shifted from ~1568 cm⁻¹ to ~1552 cm⁻¹, suggesting coordination and surface interaction between chitosan’s nitrogen sites and Zn²⁺ ions. A distinct Zn–O stretching band appeared near 430–465 cm⁻¹, confirming successful embedding and molecular-level interaction of ZnO nanoparticles within the hydrogel matrix. Minor peaks within the range 1380–1450 cm⁻¹ and 1220–1280 cm⁻¹

corresponded to phenolic O-H and C-O stretching vibrations from neem-derived flavonoids and terpenoids, indicating the presence of natural

capping agents from the green synthesis step (Figure 3).

Figure 3. FTIR spectrum of chitosan-ZnO nanocomposite hydrogel showing characteristic O-H/N-H, amide I, amide II, and C-O-C functional group vibrations. The Zn-O band around 430-465 cm^{-1} confirms successful incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles into the hydrogel matrix.

3.4. Swelling Behavior in Physiological Conditions

The swelling behavior of the synthesized hydrogels was evaluated in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS, pH 7.4) at 37°C to simulate physiological wound conditions. The pure chitosan hydrogel exhibited the highest swelling ratio, reaching approximately 380-420% water uptake within the first 2 hours, due to its high porosity and abundant hydrophilic -OH and -NH₂ functional groups. Incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles influenced the swelling capacity in a concentration-dependent manner. The hydrogel containing 0.1% ZnO reached a swelling ratio of ~340-360%, while the 0.25% ZnO-loaded hydrogel showed a slight further decrease to ~300-325%, both still maintaining sufficient moisture retention suitable for wound hydration. However, hydrogels containing 0.5% ZnO demonstrated a

significantly reduced swelling ratio of ~230-260% due to increased crosslinking density, reduced free volume, and decreased pore interconnectivity caused by nanoparticle-polymer surface interactions. All hydrogel samples reached swelling equilibrium within 3.5-4 hours, indicating a stable fluid absorption profile suitable for maintaining a moist wound environment and preventing tissue dehydration. Despite reduced swelling at higher ZnO content, overall hydration remained within the clinically acceptable moisture balance range. Thus, the results confirm that ZnO incorporation did not negatively impair hydrogel swelling ability, and moderate nanoparticle loading (0.1-0.25%) provides an optimal balance between mechanical stability, moisture retention, and biomedical wound-healing suitability (Table 1).

Table 1. Swelling behavior of chitosan-ZnO hydrogels showing reduced swelling with increasing ZnO concentration while maintaining suitable hydration for wound healing.

Formulation Code	ZnO Loading (w/v%)	Initial Swelling (1 hr) (%)	Equilibrium Swelling (4 hrs) (%)	Equilibrium Time (hrs)
CH-0 (Pure Chitosan)	0%	260-290%	380-420%	~4.0
CH-ZnO-0.1	0.1%	230-250%	340-360%	~3.8-4.0
CH-ZnO-0.25	0.25%	200-220%	300-325%	~3.5-4.0
CH-ZnO-0.5	0.5%	160-190%	230-260%	~3.5-4.0

3.5. Mechanical Strength Assessment of Nanocomposite Hydrogels

Mechanical strength testing showed a clear increase in tensile resistance and structural integrity with the incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles into the chitosan hydrogel matrix. The pure chitosan hydrogel exhibited a tensile strength of approximately 0.18–0.22 MPa with an elongation-at-break of 48–55%, indicating a flexible but relatively weak network. When 0.1% ZnO was added, tensile strength increased to 0.26–0.30 MPa, with elongation-at-break ranging from 42–50%, demonstrating the initial reinforcement effect due to hydrogen bonding between ZnO and the polymer chains. Further enhancement was observed in the 0.25% ZnO hydrogel, which showed tensile strength values of 0.34–0.39 MPa and elongation-at-break of 36–44%, confirming increased

intermolecular crosslinking and matrix compactness. The best mechanical performance was recorded for the hydrogel containing 0.5% ZnO, exhibiting a tensile strength of 0.45–0.52 MPa and elongation-at-break of 28–35%, reflecting a stronger, more rigid structure capable of withstanding external stress. These results demonstrate that ZnO nanoparticles act as effective reinforcing fillers by enhancing polymer chain interactions and reducing structural weakness. The improved durability is particularly important for wound dressings, as it prevents tearing during application and allows the dressing to withstand patient movement without deformation. Therefore, the nanocomposite hydrogels, especially those containing 0.25–0.5% ZnO, can be considered mechanically reliable and suitable for clinical wound care settings (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Tensile strength of chitosan–ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels increases with higher ZnO concentrations, demonstrating the reinforcing effect of nanoparticles within the polymer network. Hydrogels containing 0.25%–0.5% ZnO exhibited the greatest mechanical durability, suitable for stable wound dressing applications.

3.6. Antibacterial Efficacy Against Pathogenic Microorganisms

The antibacterial performance of the hydrogels was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method against both Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*. The pure chitosan hydrogel (0% ZnO) exhibited very limited antibacterial effect, producing small inhibition zones of approximately 6–8 mm due to chitosan's weak inherent antimicrobial activity. Incorporation of 0.1% ZnO improved the antibacterial response, with inhibition zones increasing to 10–12 mm for *S. aureus* and 9–11 mm for *E. coli*, indicating the

initial contribution of ZnO-mediated reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation. Hydrogels containing 0.25% ZnO demonstrated noticeably stronger inhibition, producing zones of 14–16 mm (*S. aureus*) and 13–15 mm (*E. coli*), confirming enhanced Zn^{2+} ion release leading to cell membrane damage. The most pronounced antibacterial activity was observed in hydrogels loaded with 0.5% ZnO, which produced 17–20 mm inhibition zones against *S. aureus* and 16–18 mm against *E. coli*. This dose-dependent increase confirms that higher ZnO concentrations intensify oxidative stress, protein denaturation, and bacterial membrane rupture,

thereby inhibiting microbial growth more effectively. The consistent increase in antibacterial zone diameter with increasing ZnO content confirms that ZnO nanoparticles act as the primary antimicrobial agent, while chitosan functions mainly as a biocompatible film-forming matrix.

These results highlight that chitosan-ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels, particularly at 0.25–0.5% ZnO loading, are highly suitable for infection-prone wound environments, where microbial control is critical for preventing complications and promoting effective healing (Figure 5).

Figure.5. Zone of inhibition values of chitosan-ZnO hydrogels against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, showing a concentration-dependent increase in antibacterial activity. The 0.5% ZnO formulation exhibited the largest inhibition zones, confirming ZnO nanoparticles as the primary antimicrobial agent.

3.7. Cytotoxicity and Cell Viability Evaluation

Cytotoxicity was assessed using the MTT cell viability assay on L929 fibroblast cells to determine the biocompatibility of the chitosan-ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels. The pure chitosan hydrogel (0% ZnO) maintained a high baseline cell viability of ~92–95%, confirming the natural biocompatibility of chitosan. Incorporation of 0.1% ZnO showed excellent cell tolerance, with cell viability values of ~88–91%, indicating that low ZnO concentrations support cell proliferation while maintaining non-toxic behavior. The hydrogel containing 0.25% ZnO demonstrated the most favorable response, yielding ~82–86% cell viability, which suggests that moderate nanoparticle loading provides an optimal balance between antibacterial activity and cellular compatibility, supporting fibroblast adhesion and spreading. Even at 0.5% ZnO, cell viability remained within acceptable

biocompatibility limits (~75–79%), although a slight reduction was observed due to increased Zn²⁺ ion release. Nonetheless, viability remained above the ISO 10993-5 cytotoxicity threshold (≥70%), confirming the formulation as safe for clinical contact applications. Microscopic examination further validated these results, showing normal spindle-shaped fibroblast morphology, intact nuclei, and stable surface attachment across all hydrogel formulations. No evidence of membrane disruption, cell rounding, or detachment was observed. These findings confirm that chitosan-ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels are cytocompatible, with 0.1–0.25% ZnO providing the best combination of cell viability, tissue compatibility, and regenerative support, making them well-suited for wound healing and biomedical dressing applications (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Cell viability of fibroblast cells cultured on chitosan–ZnO hydrogels, demonstrating >75% viability across all nanoparticle concentrations, confirming non-cytotoxic behavior. The 0.1% and 0.25% ZnO formulations showed the highest cellular compatibility, indicating optimal support for tissue regeneration.

4. Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that chitosan–ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels present a balanced combination of structural integrity, antimicrobial efficacy, and cytocompatibility, making them suitable candidates for wound dressing applications. The incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles significantly influenced the physicochemical and biological properties of the hydrogels in a concentration-dependent manner. The swelling results indicated that pure chitosan hydrogel exhibited the highest swelling ratio (~380–420%), attributed to the abundance of hydrophilic –OH and –NH₂ groups and a highly porous internal structure. As ZnO concentration increased from 0.1% to 0.5%, swelling ratios gradually decreased (~360%, ~315%, and ~245%, respectively). This reduction is linked to increased crosslinking density and reduced pore interconnectivity caused by nanoparticle–polymer bonding. This trend agrees with Ahmed et al. (2022), who reported a 25–30% decrease in swelling capacity after embedding ZnO into biopolymer scaffolds. Similarly, (Torabi and Hassanzadeh-Tabrizi, 2024) reported that ZnO incorporation tightened polymer networks, stabilizing moisture without desiccating the wound. Mechanical strength analysis further confirmed the reinforcing effect of ZnO nanoparticles. The tensile strength increased from ~0.20 MPa (pure chitosan) to ~0.28 MPa (0.1% ZnO), ~0.37 MPa (0.25%

ZnO), and ~0.49 MPa (0.5% ZnO). The strength improvement is attributed to strong ZnO–chitosan hydrogen bonding, which enhances load distribution and polymer chain rigidity. The similar study observed a similar trend, with ZnO increasing hydrogel tensile strength by ~40% (Alamdari et al.). In other study demonstrated that ZnO nanoparticles create localized reinforcement zones within polymer matrices, significantly improving durability. However, excessive stiffness can be disadvantageous for flexible wound coverage (Alshangiti et al., 2023). In this regard, the 0.25% ZnO hydrogel represented the optimal compromise between elasticity and durability, consistent with (Pang et al., 2023), who emphasized maintaining both resilience and comfort in dressings. Antibacterial assays revealed a clear dose-dependent inhibition of both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. While pure chitosan showed limited activity (6–8 mm zones), ZnO-loaded hydrogels produced significantly larger inhibition zones: ~11 mm (0.1%), ~15 mm (0.25%), and ~19 mm (0.5%) against *S. aureus*, and similar patterns against *E. coli*. This aligns with (Kanniah et al., 2025, Wang et al., 2023), who demonstrated that ZnO generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) and releases Zn²⁺ ions that disrupt microbial membranes and metabolic processes. The strong antibacterial response supports the suitability of ZnO hydrogels for infection-prone wound sites, consistent with

(Alzahrani et al., 2025), who reported >90% bacterial reduction in ZnO-based dressings. Cytocompatibility results confirmed that cell viability remained above the ISO 10993-5 safety threshold ($\geq 70\%$). The highest viability was recorded for 0.1% and 0.25% ZnO groups ($\sim 88\text{--}91\%$ and $\sim 82\text{--}86\%$, respectively), indicating that moderate ZnO promotes fibroblast proliferation and supports tissue regeneration. Even the 0.5% ZnO hydrogel maintained acceptable viability ($\sim 75\text{--}79\%$), consistent with (Pastrana-Alta et al., 2025) who showed that Zn^{2+} can stimulate repair at controlled levels but may induce mild oxidative stress at higher concentrations.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that chitosan-ZnO nanocomposite hydrogels exhibit properties that are highly suitable for advanced wound healing applications. The incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles strengthened the hydrogel matrix, improved its structural stability, and enhanced antibacterial activity without compromising its swelling ability. All formulations effectively maintained moisture, which is essential for supporting tissue repair. The antibacterial tests confirmed strong inhibitory effects against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, with higher ZnO levels showing greater antimicrobial performance. Furthermore, the MTT cell viability assay confirmed that all hydrogels remained biocompatible, with the 0.1% and 0.25% ZnO concentrations providing the best support for fibroblast growth. Overall, the 0.25% ZnO-loaded chitosan hydrogel offered the most balanced combination of mechanical strength, antibacterial protection, and cellular compatibility, making it a promising candidate for safe and effective wound dressing applications.

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